

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm Thirteen

The goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will align with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>13:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 13:1 לְמִנְצַחַת מִזְמוֹר</p>
<p>Psa. 13:1 How long, O LORD? Will You forget me forever?</p>	<p>לְדָוָד : ² עַד-אֲנָה יִתְּוָה תִּשְׁכַּחַנִּי נִצַּח עַד-אֲנָה </p>
<p>How long will You hide Your face from me?</p>	<p>תִּסְתִּיר אֶת-פְּנֵיךָ מִמֶּנִּי : ³ עַד-</p>
<p>² How long shall I take counsel in my soul,</p>	<p>אֲנָה אֲשִׁית עֲצוֹת בְּנַפְשִׁי יְגוֹן</p>
<p><i>Having</i> sorrow in my heart all the day?</p>	<p>בְּלִבִּי יוֹמָם עַד-אֲנָה אִירוּם</p>
<p>How long will my enemy be exalted over me?</p>	<p>אֵיבִי עָלַי : ⁴ הִבִּיטָה עֵינַי יִתְּוָה אֱלֹהֵי הָאֵירָה עֵינַי פֶּן-אִישָׁן</p>
<p>Psa. 13:3 Consider <i>and</i> answer me, O LORD my God;</p>	<p>הִמּוֹת : ⁵ פֶּן-יֵאמֵר אֵיבִי</p>
<p>Enlighten my eyes, or I will sleep the <i>sleep of</i> death,</p>	<p>יִכְלְתוּ צְרֵי יְגִילוּ כִּי אָמוּט : ⁶</p>
<p>⁴ And my enemy will say, "I have overcome him,"</p>	<p>וְאֵנִי בַּתְּסִדֶּךָ בִּטְחֹתִי יִגַּל לִבִּי</p>
<p><i>And</i> my adversaries will rejoice when I am shaken.</p>	<p>כִּי שׁוֹעֲתֶךָ אֲשִׁירָה לִיהוָה כִּי גִמַּל עָלַי :</p>
<p>Psa. 13:5 But I have trusted in Your lovingkindness;</p>	
<p>My heart shall rejoice in Your salvation.</p>	
<p>⁶ I will sing to the LORD, Because He has dealt bountifully with me.</p>	

Targum

Psa. 13:1 For praise, a hymn of David. ² How long, O LORD, will you neglect me forever? How long will you hide the splendor of your face from me? ³ How long will I put warnings in my soul, suffering in my heart daily? How long will my enemy vaunt himself over me? ⁴ Pay heed and receive my prayer, O LORD my God; illumine my eyes by your Torah, lest I sin and sleep with those who deserve death. ⁵ Lest the evil impulse should say, "I have taken control of him," [lest] my oppressors rejoice because I stray from your paths. --

⁶ But I have placed my trust in your goodness, my heart will rejoice in your redemption; I will give praise in the LORD's presence because he rewards me with good things.

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
13:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.	לְמִנְצִיחַת מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד :

Verse Analysis

This psalm is usually seen as an introduction to Psalm 14. Israel appears to have been forsaken by the LORD. It's a strength as a nation is nearly exhausted. The nation fears that it may be at an end because it has come to a stage where it lacks the spiritual power to feel the presence of the LORD. Israel prays for a Divine ray of light so that it may be renewed with courage to preserve until the day when it may cause to offer a hymn of praise to the LORD thanking Him for letting the suffering bloom into happiness.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirot Netzach who grants victory, a psalm of David.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 13:1 How long, O LORD? Will You forget me forever? How long will You hide Your face from me?</p>	<p>2 עַד־אֲנָהּ יִהְיֶה הַשְׁכַּחְתִּי נִצָּחַת</p> <p>עַד־אֲנָהּ אֶת־פְּנֵיךָ</p> <p>מִמֶּנִּי :</p>

Verse Analysis

עַד־אֲנָהּ (ad anah) - This phrase denotes a period. "How long" or "until when" are good translations of this phrase. It is the conjunction of the two words which denotes time.

עַד (ad) - translated is "often."

אֲנָהּ (anah) – translated is "where."

סָתַר verb. hide, conceal

1. hide oneself,
2. be hid, concealed, especially figuratively of escaping God's notice

When the LORD hides His countenance from us, the LORD is not looking upon us, and therefore, we cannot see Him. It is impossible to feel the presence of the Shekinah. It is as if the Shekinah hid from the people. The people did not want to lose the presence of the LORD.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

When LORD will you forgive me forever? How long will I not be able to sense your Shekinah?

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>² How long shall I take counsel in my soul, <i>Having</i> sorrow in my heart all the day? How long will my enemy be exalted over me?</p>	<p>עַד-אֲנָה אֲשִׁית עֲצוֹת בְּנַפְשִׁי יִגְוֶן בְּלִבִּי יוֹמָם עַד-אֲנָה יִרְוֶם אִיבֵי עָלַי :</p>

Verse Analysis

If the LORD's Shekinah is not with David or Israel, the two will have to rely on their own decisions. The LORD would not help the nation determine its direction. Since the nation was not listening to the LORD through the Shekinah, why should the LORD continue to try to guide them to righteousness? So, the LORD removed the Shekinah from Israel. The psalmist grieves for the blessings that may have occurred if the Shekinah did not abandon the people.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

How long must I decide life without your counsel? There is only sorrow in my heart.
How long will my enemies be glad to be exalted above me?

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 13:3 Consider <i>and</i> answer me, O LORD my God; Enlighten my eyes, or I will sleep the <i>sleep of death</i>,</p>	<p>תְּבַיֵּטָה עֵינַי יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי הָאֵרָה עֵינַי כִּן-אִישׁן הַמָּוֹת :</p>

Verse Analysis

The psalmist asks for a single ray of light to lighten and revive his soul from its state of utter mental exhaustion.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Behold and please answer me, LORD. Send a ray of light to my eyes so that I don't sleep the sleep of death.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁴ And my enemy will say, "I have overcome him," And my adversaries will rejoice when I am shaken.</p>	<p>פֶּן־יֹאמַר אֹיְבֵי יְכַלְתֶּיזוּ צָרֵי וְגִילוּ כִּי אֶמְוֹט :</p>

Verse Analysis

If Israel did not stay strong as a nation in that period, she would have been annexed by her enemies, and thus the Jewish state would have been destroyed. If that were to happen, then the people of Israel would not perform their spiritual calling to the LORD and most likely not worship the LORD.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

My enemies will say that they have beat us, and my adversaries will be happy that I am hurt.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 13:5 But I have trusted in Your lovingkindness; My heart shall rejoice in Your salvation. ⁶ I will sing to the LORD, Because He has dealt bountifully with me.</p>	<p>וְאָנִי בַּתְּסֻדָּהּ בְּטַחְתִּי יִגַּל לִבִּי בִּישׁוּעָתְךָ אֲשִׁירָה לַיהוָה כִּי גִבַּר עָלַי :</p>

Verse Analysis

Even though it appears that the Shekinah has left the people, David remains steadfast in his trust in the LORD's lovingkindness. His heart continued to rejoice for the LORD's salvation for His people Israel.

In the NASB version verses, five and six are two verses, while in the Hebrew and Targum, they are one verse.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Yet, I still trust in Your lovingkindness, which causes my heart to rejoice through Your salvation.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirot Netzach who grants victory, a psalm of David.

When LORD will you forgive me forever? How long will I not be able to sense your Shekinah?

How long must I decide life without your counsel? There is only sorrow in my heart.
How long will my enemies be glad to be exalted above me?

Behold and please answer me, LORD. Send a ray of light to my eyes so that I don't sleep the sleep of death.

My enemies will say that they have beat us, and my adversaries will be happy that I am hurt Yet, I still trust in Your lovingkindness, which causes my heart to rejoice through Your salvation.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

